

ANALYSIS OF COMPLIANCE WITH THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE STANDARD OF GOOD PHARMACY PRACTICE IN PHARMACY ORGANIZATIONS IN ASTANA

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Annotation. Good pharmacy practice is aimed at providing the population with high-quality, safe and effective medicines and medical products, providing reliable information about drugs, encouraging a healthy lifestyle, ensuring the reasonable use of prescription drugs and providing proper advice during self-medication[1].

Keywords: good pharmacy practice, good pharmacy practice, standard of good pharmacy practice, pharmacist, pharmacist.

The relevance of the topic. Today, the implementation of the standard of good pharmacy practice in pharmacy organizations is a priority task. Since, from January 1, 2023, in accordance with the Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 7, 2020 No. 360-VI of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On the Health of the people and the healthcare system", the requirement of compliance with the standard of good pharmacy practice for pharmacy organizations is mandatory[2].

The problem of rational and safe use of medicines is one of the important problems of modern health management. To solve them, in 1992, the International Pharmaceutical Federation developed standards for pharmacy services called Good Pharmacy Practice or "Good Pharmacy Practice", which were approved by the World Health Organization in March 1993.

The Guide to Good Pharmacy practice describes the necessary actions to promote health and prevent deterioration of the health status of the population, and, if necessary, treatment - ensuring the correct use of medicines in order to achieve maximum therapeutic effect and prevent adverse effects of the drug. These actions assume that pharmacists, together with other healthcare professionals, as well as with patients, take collective responsibility for the results of treatment [3].

The Guidelines on Good Pharmacy Practice establish standards for the circulation of medicines from the moment when the medicine is ready for sale until it reaches the consumer and is used by them. The standards include activities on health promotion and disease prevention, on the supply and use of prescribed medicines, as well as medical devices, on self-medication, and contain recommendations on how to influence the prescription and use of medicines.

The basic idea of good pharmacy practice is to focus on the well-being of the patient. In this regard, the purpose of good pharmacy practice is to create quality standards for pharmacy services in the name of: improving public health; regulating the mechanism of supply and sale of medicines and medical devices; proper organization of self-treatment of patients; pharmaceutical activities should be based on: guaranteed quality of medicines and medical devices, information and consulting support, control the effectiveness of the use of medicines and medical devices; an integral part of the pharmacist's contribution should be the promotion of rational and economical (from the point of view of pharmacoeconomics) prescription and use of medicines; each of the services of the pharmaceutical service should be relevant for each person, clearly defined and understandable for those to whom the services are provided [4].

The purpose of the study. To study and analyze compliance with the requirements of good pharmacy practice by subjects of drug circulation in pharmacy organizations in Astana.

Research methods. To achieve this goal, an analysis of scientific publications, reports of the World Health Organization, regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of

Kazakhstan was carried out. The object of the study was the knowledge of the subjects of the circulation of medicines of the rules of prescription, storage and release of medicines as the main components of good pharmacy practice. The study was conducted by face-to-face anonymous questioning of pharmaceutical specialists and was descriptive in nature. A total of 125 Astana specialists were interviewed. The observation method was used to study the qualifications of the employees of the first table in pharmacy organizations.

Main results and conclusions. In order to study the awareness of the rules of storage of drugs requiring special storage conditions, pharmacy specialists were asked the following questions. The first issue concerned the storage of thermolabile preparations. To the question "how long can a thermolabile drug be stored without a refrigerator?" only 68% of pharmacy specialists answered "not at all", 16% each answered "1 hour" and "12 hours". To the question "where should medicines requiring protection from light be stored?" 58% of pharmaceutical specialists answered "in closets", 10% - "in cabinets using reflective film or blinds" and 32% indicated that they "do not require special storage conditions if packaged in secondary packaging." The answers showed that pharmacy specialists do not clearly represent the rules for storing medicines that require special storage conditions, and therefore violate the rules, which can lead to a decrease in the quality of medicines during storage.

The most serious problems with compliance with the requirements of good pharmacy practice were identified by us in the process of studying the prescription and release of medicines. .

Knowledge and observance of the basic principles of storage of medicines and medical devices is mandatory for all subjects of circulation of medicines, given that any violation or deviation from regulated storage conditions can lead to a decrease in their quality (change in activity, increase in toxicity, decrease in shelf life) and be unsafe for the patient. In order to ensure proper storage conditions, appropriate facilities and equipment are needed.

1. The basic requirements of good pharmacy practice aimed at improving the health of the population and the well-being of each person are not respected by all subjects of the circulation of medicines. Pharmaceutical specialists are not familiar enough with the regulatory framework for the prescription, storage and release of medicines, which leads to a decrease in the safety of the use of medicines.

2. The division of responsibilities and contact between doctors and pharmacy workers in the process of providing medicines to the population has been lost, continuity of actions of subjects of drug circulation is not ensured and the responsibility of the parties for the results of treatment is blurred.

3. To get out of this situation, it is necessary to strengthen interaction between medical and pharmaceutical specialists and increase the responsibility of each specialist for the results of his activities.

Literature.

1. Durmanova M.I. New in the GPP standard. Information and analytical newspaper "Kazakhstan Pharmaceutical Bulletin" No. 9 (608), May 2021

2. " On the Health of the people and the healthcare system" Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 7, 2020 No. 360-VI of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan 233-3 <https://adilet.zan.kz/kaz/docs/K2000000360>

3. Mostovoy A. Proper pharmacy practice: transfer pharmacies from the state of "as is" to the state of "as it should be" // Moscow pharmacies. - 2017. No. 10. – pp.21-26.

4. Gnausheva I.A. GPP – proper pharmacy practice // Pharmacy and market.-2020. No. 1-From 25-29.